

KITBASHING APPARATUS IN ARCHITECTURE: Toward Sustainable Assemblage Practices

IREM SEZER

AIA Virginia

remsezer@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, architecture has increasingly embraced unconventional methods for form generation, with kitbashing emerging as a notable practice. Originally associated with aesthetic experimentation, kitbashing involves the assembly of prefabricated or found components in unexpected ways. This paper explores the potential of kitbashing to address ecological challenges in architecture by repurposing reclaimed, upcycled, and recycled materials, thereby reducing waste and resource consumption. Through the integration of advanced technologies, such as robotic arms and 3D printing, kitbashing can contribute to sustainable construction practices. The research examines how disassembly and reassembly techniques can minimize the environmental footprint of building processes while promoting innovative design solutions. By repositioning kitbashing as a tool for sustainable architecture, this paper presents speculative design opportunities that challenge traditional material use and emphasize adaptability. Focusing on various typologies, the study demonstrates how kitbashing can shift the paradigms of architectural design and construction. Ultimately, this research provides a new framework for considering the environmental implications of kitbashing, highlighting its potential to offer innovative solutions for future architectural practices in response to pressing ecological concerns.

1. INTRODUCTION

Aesthetic discussions in architecture are central to the profession. Architects, educators, and theorists often debate the role of objects in architecture, whether as components of a larger system or as the architectural object itself. These discussions frequently explore the aesthetics of objects, the relationships between parts, part-to-whole dynamics, and their connection to the broader context. Architecture inherently involves the design and assembly of different elements, materials, and components, creating a constant dialogue about the tension and relationships between discrete objects. These discussions encompass aesthetics, theory, criticism, and the history of architectural movements, styles, and material juxtapositions. In recent years, architecture has increasingly explored unconventional methods for form generation such as parametric design, generative design, robotic fabrication, and experimental assemblages, and more specifically, the kitbashing method. Kitbashing involves taking prefabricated kits or components and assembling them in unexpected, often experimental ways. Traditionally associated with model-making rather than architecture, kitbashing has begun to intersect with architectural experimentation, particularly within the context of speculative realism and object-oriented ontology, where the relationships between objects and their components are central, and focusing on the aesthetics and philosophy of architectural objects, emphasizing their part-to-part and part-to-whole relationships. However, this paper argues for a different perspective: extending kitbashing beyond its aesthetic and philosophical origins to address sustainability and adaptability. By leveraging kitbashing's inherent ethos of reusing found components and materials, architects can design projects that not only create room for aesthetics but are also environmentally responsible and sustainable. The sustainability challenges in architecture are pressing, issues like construction waste, resource depletion, and the Anthropocene era's impact on the environment highlight the critical position for architects to discuss responsible practices. Kitbashing offers a pathway to reduce the environmental footprint of construction by reclaiming materials from abandoned or demolished buildings, incorporating material innovations and technological apparatus. When a building is slated for demolition, its components are often undervalued, however, kitbashing encourages architects to see these materials as valuable resources that can be repurposed for new designs. By embracing this method of designing, architects can significantly contribute to decarbonization efforts while maintaining the architectonic qualities of their projects.

This paper seeks to bridge the gap between kitbashing's aesthetic origins and its potential for sustainable architectural practices through the use of reclaimed materials, upcycled or recycled components, and advanced technologies advocating that kitbashing can evolve into a tool for creating adaptable, environmentally responsible designs.

2. KITBASHING AS AN EPISTEMOLOGICAL SHIFT

The work of architects such as Mark Foster Gage and Andrew Kovacs provide a foundation for understanding kitbashing in architecture. Gage's high-resolution architectural object experiments (Figure 1) and Kovacs and Gassaway's Architectural Cliff (Figure 2) exemplify the potential of kitbashing to challenge traditional design aesthetics.

Figure 1:
Mark Foster Gage, Helsinki
Guggenheim Museum

Gage describes kitbashing as the assembly of objects as separate entities, resulting in non-syntactic architectural structures (Gage, 2017). He highlights Kovacs' work as following similar principles, wherein architectural components are assembled in ways that defy conventional logic and order. Kovacs and Gassaway describe their work as oscillating between a collection and a hoard, where architectural objects are collected and acquired from various sources around New York City (Kovacs & Gassaway, 2014). Hans Tursack writes about Andrew Kovacs's assemblages: "Andrew Kovacs's collections and projects where bits of architectural history are chopped up to make a confetti of parts and then slapped together in a sunnier version of a Mad Max fortress. The sheer number of parts, breadth of selection high and low, generic and noteworthy, and all-over distribution in projects like his Proposal for Collective Living (Bust of Medusa) end up reading more as pattern than as complexity and difference. (Tursack, 2017).

The precise collision and compaction of these objects form a three-dimensional spatial coalition that defies traditional design norms. While these examples are powerful explorations of architectural form and aesthetics, they do not explicitly engage with the environmental implications of the kitbashing process. Both Gage's and Kovacs' works emphasize the assembly of found objects or purposefully created components to open up discussions about architectural objects and aesthetics. However, their work does not focus on the environmental impact of material use, resource extraction, or the potential for reducing the carbon footprint through sustainable design practices.

Figure 2:
Andrew Kovacs & Chris
Gassaway, Architectural Cliff

Kitbashing in architecture, as seen in the works of Gage and Kovacs, is associated with aesthetic and theoretical design experimentation—parts and objects assembled in unconventional ways. However, if we consider reframing its critical position within the context of decarbonization practices, extending beyond form and aesthetic discussions, the following questions arise: How can the disassembly and reassembly of materials contribute to more sustainable architectural design practices? How can kitbashing reduce waste, encourage the reuse of materials, and promote environmental stewardship in the built environment while preserving the aesthetic quality of the object? Moreover, is this method an experiment in changing how we approach architectural design?

Kitbashing challenges traditional notions of design by embracing fragmentation, hybridity, and experimentation. It also encourages rethinking the relationships between materials, tectonics, and form, breaking down and recombining elements to create something new.

It begins with available materials and found objects, disrupting conventional ideas of architectural authorship and originality. By generating unexpected juxtapositions and assemblies, kitbashing opens new possibilities for creating forms that are as thought-provoking as they are resource-efficient. This practice, therefore, calls for a new discourse; one that positions kitbashing within the framework of ecological design practices. Rather than solely focusing on designing every bit and part, kitbashing prioritizes the organization and relationships between objects. However, this approach is not limited to just manual assembly or ad hoc practices. Kitbashing also embraces technological advancements such as robotic design, generative tools, and innovative materials. By integrating these components, it becomes possible to create sustainable, adaptable, and aesthetic structures that redefine how architects think about materials, processes, and the environment. The method pushes the conversation further and explores how it can be an effective strategy for utilizing reclaimed, upcycled, and recycled materials while incorporating technological apparatus during the assembly process. The concept of 'form follows availability' becomes particularly relevant in this context, as the availability of materials influences the design process and challenges architects to think creatively about how to assemble and reassemble components. This approach encourages a shift in architectural design thinking, where material availability, rather than predefined design rules, directs the final form. Furthermore, the idea of 'form follows innovative materiality' emerges as an equally critical framework, highlighting the aesthetic and sustainable potential of kitbashing.

2.1 THE ROADMAP OF SUSTAINABLE KITBASHING METHOD

New Discourse and Design Experimentation:

Kitbashing creates a tension on fragmentation and hybridity, generating unexpected juxtapositions and tensions between materials, forms, and assembly. The aesthetic quality emerges from the creative interplay of contrasts—old and new, rough and refined, smooth and sharp, low-resolution and high-resolution, found and fabricated. This "imperfection" and "collage-like quality" challenges conventional understanding of aesthetics, and creates a new discourse ground for its design philosophy of experimentation.

Kitbashing advocates that sustainability does not mean sacrificing aesthetics. Instead, it demonstrates that the aesthetic tensions between discrete parts can be a defining feature of its architectonic qualities.

Rethinking Design Authorship:

Kitbashing disrupts traditional ideas of architectural authorship by creating fragmented, hybrid assemblies. These assemblages combine objects from different eras, materials from diverse origins, and

construction techniques ranging from traditional craftsmanship to robotics. This synthesis challenges the notion of singular authorship, instead positioning the architect as a curator of components and materials.

Designing for Uncertainty:

Kitbashing also questions unpredictable availability of materials and conditions. Key questions arise: What materials are accessible? How can discrete parts be assembled or curated? What innovative methods or technologies can be incorporated? How can disassembly be planned for future reuse? By embracing uncertainty, constraints are reframed as opportunities for creativity.

Ecological Design Practices and Incorporating Technology:

Kitbashing positions itself as a critique of linear design and construction processes. Instead, it advocates for a circular approach where materials continuously re-enter the design cycle. It opens a theoretical and practical discourse that connects material ethics, design innovation, and aesthetic exploration. While kitbashing begins with found objects, it does not limit itself to existing materials. It incorporates advancements in material science and digital tools, creating a hybrid approach that blends resourcefulness with technological precision. This allows architects to experiment with robotic fabrication, generative design, and material prototyping, elevating kitbashing beyond manual or ad hoc practices. The method is not limited to manual assembly; it can incorporate robotics, parametric, generative tools, and 3D printing to expand material use possibilities. These tools enable precise cutting, joining, and adaptation of materials, making the process more efficient while maintaining aesthetics and tectonic features.

Disassembly and Reassembly:

Kitbashing encourages the breakdown of existing structures that would be decommissioned, components, and materials, viewing them as opportunities for reuse rather than waste. By designing for disassembly, materials can be reclaimed at the end of a structure's lifecycle, promoting circularity. This reduces the need for raw material extraction and minimizes construction waste, directly addressing issues of resource depletion and carbon emissions. For example, salvaging steel beams or wooden planks from a demolished building and recombining them in new ways extends their lifecycle and prevents landfill accumulation.

2.2 MATERIALS, TECHNOLOGIES, AND OPPORTUNITIES

This discourse on kitbashing as a practice in the context of ecologically responsive architecture opens up new opportunities and projections towards material and technological innovations. The adjacency of new and old materials could create an aesthetic and structural tension;

however, it may also reveal technology as the adhesive—the glue of the design. By this, I mean incorporating software and engaging 3D printing and fabrication techniques. These methods could connect the different parts, providing various assemblage opportunities. The material science of architecture is also undergoing transformation, as we can see from recent studies on recycled materials and biomaterials being experimented with on the architectural design scale. There are also numerous material investigations that will soon be tested (see Transmaterials, MIT Media Lab, etc.). Another branch of material studies focuses on reclaimed materials and transforming waste materials. Cork blocks by MPH Architects, Seratech by Sam Draper and Barney Shanks, Biogenic Limestone by Minus Materials, concrete vaulted flooring by ACORN, Carbicrete by McGill University, Sea Stone by Newtab-22, FoamWork by ETH Zurich, K-Briq by Kenoteq, Building the Local by Ellie Birkhead, Gent Waste Brick by Carmody Groarke, TRANS Architectuur Stedenbouw, Local Works Studio, BC Materials, Green Charcoal Bricks by the Indian School of Design and Innovation, Mycelium Brick by The Living, Urine Bio-Bricks by Suzanne Lambert, and Cob Bricks by Tavs Jorgensen are just a few examples of reclaimed and biomaterials that can be a ‘part’ in kitbashing architecture.

Figure 3:
Photo courtesy of Newtab-22,
Sea Stone

Figure 4:
Photo courtesy of Patrick
Bedarf, FoamWork by ETH
Zurich

These innovations aim to reduce carbon footprints and construction impacts, while also contributing to the sustainability and aesthetics discourse of kitbashing, particularly through the tension created by the juxtaposition of parts, components, and elements. For example, Germany's entry for the 2023 Venice Architecture Biennale features a large collection of materials salvaged from the previous biennale, now can be repurposed for various uses across the city. These materials, sourced from over 40 installations, have been meticulously gathered and cataloged, with plans to use them for repairs and improvements to buildings and public spaces throughout Venice. Titled *Open for Maintenance*, the exhibition presents itself as "an action framework for a new building culture" (Frearson, 2023). The team explains the work as follows: Constructed entirely from surplus materials left behind by the Biennale Arte 2022, which generated hundreds of tons of waste, the pavilion serves as functional infrastructure. It advocates for reuse, circular construction, and the integration of social responsibility into architectural practices (Germany Pavilion Team, 2023).

It is also possible to discuss kitbashing on different scales beyond its materiality and discreteness. Kitbashing can range from small objects or furniture to pavilions, public space objects, or large-scale architectural projects. The difference in scale also manifests

itself in the method of assemblage, ranging from DIY practices and hand-crafted montages to robotic assemblies and the integration of automation in the building process.

Figure 5:
**The German Pavilion, Venice
Architecture Biennale 2023**

3. CONCLUSION

Kitbashing offers a promising pathway for addressing ecological challenges in architecture by shifting the focus from being solely an aesthetic experimentation to sustainability, materiality, and the aesthetics of its architectonics. By leveraging reclaimed, upcycled, and recycled materials, kitbashing reduces resource consumption and waste while encouraging modular, disassemblable designs that extend material life cycles and promote a circular economy. These practices not only minimize the environmental impact of construction but also inspire new approaches to designing adaptable and sustainable structures. One of the key innovations of kitbashing lies in its potential to challenge conventional design norms and embrace experimental aesthetics. By emphasizing principles like “form follows availability” and “form follows innovative materiality,” the method provides a dynamic interplay between aesthetic exploration and environmental responsibility. Compared to traditional construction methods, kitbashing has the advantage of reimagining waste as a resource while reducing dependency on new materials.

To fully harness its potential, further research is needed on material sourcing networks, policy frameworks, and community-based applications. Exploring its implementation in diverse cultural, ecological, and technological contexts will expand its applicability and relevance. Integrating advanced technologies will be crucial for enhancing efficiency and scalability while preserving the experimental and aesthetic qualities of the practice.

In conclusion, kitbashing repositions architecture to address pressing environmental concerns while fostering innovation and creativity. It bridges the gap between sustainability and aesthetics, offering a fresh perspective on how materials, forms, and construction methods can evolve in harmony with ecological and social responsibility, reinforcing its potential as a critical tool for decarbonization and sustainable design practices.

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